

2.5 cm of soil was removed and dried either in a hot air oven at 60°C for 24 hours or in sunlight for 2 to 3 days, This soil was used as inoculant. Normally, zygotes sprout into small seedlings 10 to 15 days after inoculation and mature

sporophytes develop within 20-25 days. The oven-dried zygotes germinated within 10-12 days; sun-dried zygotes germinated in 18-20 days.

The laboratory method allows researchers to raise azolla fronds from dried

materials and to transport azolla seed inoculum (dried zygotes), without damaging seed viability. This technique may also solve storage problems, sowing limitations imposed by summer, and help in azolla crossbreeding. □

Effect of summer plowing with different implements on wetland rice yields

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The effect of summer plowing with different implements on wetland rice yield and weed dry matter accumulation was studied during 1980 and 1981. Treatments were no tillage (control), plowing with country plow, tractor-drawn 11-tined cultivator, and tractor-drawn disc plow. Land was tilled in April and rice was transplanted in early July after puddling with a 10-hp power tiller. Soil was a sandy clay loam.

Plots tilled by disc plow had lowest weed population and yielded highest (see table). Weed dry matter accumulation was lowest after disc plowing,

Effect of summer plowing with different implements on rice grain yield and weed dry matter accumulation.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)			Weed dry matter accumulation (t/ha)		
	1980	1981	Mean	1980	1981	Mean
Control	2.4	2.0	2.2	2.1	2.7	2.4
Country plow	2.8	2.1	2.4	1.7	2.0	1.8
Cultivator	3.1	2.2	2.6	1.5	1.6	1.5
Disc plow	3.8	2.6	3.2	0.9	1.2	1.1
Mean	3.0	2.2	2.6	1.5	1.9	1.7
CD at 5%	0.1	0.2		0.1	0.04	

amounting to 0.9 t/ha in 1980 and 1.2 t/ha in 1981, followed by values for the cultivator and country plow.

Weed flora consisted mostly of *Cyperus rotundus* L., *Echinochloa crus-galli* (L.) Beauv., *Monochoria hastata* (L.) Solms, *Paspalum scrobiculatum* L., *Panicum* spp., *Hygrophila spinosa* T. Anders., *Oxalis* spp., *Emilia sonchifolia*

(L.) DC. ex Wight, *Setaria glauca* (L.) Beauv., *Cynodon dactylon* (L.) Pers., *Sporobolus diander* (Retz.) Beauv., *Chrysopogon* spp., *Caesulia axillaris* Roxb., *Saponaria vaccaria* L., *Spergula arvensis* L., *Jussiaea suffruticosa* L., *Polygonum plebeium* R. Br., and *Ageratum conyzoides* L., in decreasing order of population. □

Response of irrigated dry seeded rice to nitrogen level, interrow spacing, and seeding rate in a semiarid environment

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Semiarid soils are inherently nitrogen deficient, which limits rice yields. Although nitrogen fertilizers are expensive and unavailable in adequate quantities in many developing countries, relatively high rice yields can be obtained by optimizing spacing of rice plants in the field. We studied the interrelationship of nitrogen level, plant population and distribution pattern, and rice yield.

Three field experiments were conducted at the Gezira Research Station (13°30' – 15°5'N and 32°30' – 33°30' E) during 1977-79. Climate is semiarid and most rains (350-400 mm) fall during July and August. Soils are dark cracking Vertisols with 40-65% clay content.

Effect of nitrogen level, interrow spacing, and seeding rates on grain yield and some major yield components of irrigated dry seeded rice IR2053-206-1-36 in a semiarid environment in Sudan Gezira (av of 3 seasons 1977-79).

	Yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grains (no./panicle)	1000-grain weight (g)
<i>N (kg/ha)</i>				
60	4.2	343.2	70.8	23.17
120	4.8	386.6	78.3	23.64
180	6.4	411.1	80.1	23.91
<i>Interrow spacing (cm)</i>				
15	5.3	464.9	75.1	23.56
20	5.6	367.0	76.8	23.56
25	5.5	310.1	77.4	23.60
<i>Seeding rate (kg/ha)</i>				
50	5.5	358.7	82.2	23.48
100	4.4	382.8	76.5	23.64
150	5.5	400.5	70.5	23.60
S. E.	0.024	5.43	1.42	0.096

Treatments were 60, 120, and 180 kg N/ha as urea; 15, 20, and 25 cm interrow spacings; and 50, 100, and 150 kg seeds/ha. Treatments were grown in a randomized complete block design with

four replications. Land was prepared dry by plowing, disc harrowing, and leveling, then was divided by heavy ridges into 3.8 × 8.0 m plots. Immediately before seeding, 6.2 kg P/ha as superphosphate

was incorporated into the soil. Urea was topdressed in equal splits at 10, 45, and 75 days after IR2053-206-1-3-6 rice emerged. Weeds and water were controlled throughout the growing season.

At harvest, 50 panicles were randomly collected from each plot and number of filled grains per panicle and grain weight were recorded. The number of panicles per square meter was determined

for five 1-m rows randomly selected from each plot, and the center 3×7 m of each plot was harvested to determine grain yield. Data obtained over the three seasons were analyzed.

The results (see table) indicate that grain yield and all major yield components significantly and progressively increased with increased nitrogen application ($P < 0.001$). Interrow 20-cm spacing

produced higher grain yield than the other spacings used ($P < 0.001$). However, the close spacing produced more panicles/m², but fewer grains per panicle. Similarly, the 150 kg/ha seed rate produced more panicles per square meter but less grains per panicle. The differences in grain yield between the seeding rates were not significant. □

Environment and its influence

Panicle transpiration measurement with a potometer

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Several studies on rice plant-water relationships have indicated the importance of panicle contribution to total plant water use during the flowering/heading stage.

A simple, inexpensive, rapid method, using a potometer, was used to estimate the transpiration rate of excised panicles. The potometer is portable and can be used in the field or laboratory (Fig. 1). Panicles were excised under water to prevent cavitation of the water column in the xylem by air bubbles. They were sealed into the potometer with parafilm and silicone sealant.

Potometers were placed under a fluorescent-incandescent light bank, which provided about $405 \mu\text{Em}^{-2} \text{sec}^{-1}$ irradiance at the top of the panicle. Air velocity was maintained at 1.9ms^{-1} and passed uniformly through 4×4 cm baffles. Panicle temperature was measured by inserting copper-constantan thermocouples into the spikelets. A shielded-aspirated psychrometer was used to measure water vapor pressure deficit of the air. Water uptake, which should be in equilibrium with transpiration in a steady state system, was determined by changes in the level of meniscus in the pipette measured at 15-minute intervals. To refill the pipette, water was injected through the surgical tubing using a hypodermic needle. The pipette was covered

1. A potometer setup for measurement of panicle transpiration.

2. Water uptake of excised IR36 panicles measured with a potometer. Vapor pressure deficit of the air = 1.652 ± 0.0196 kPa, panicle temperature = $24.21 \pm .062^\circ\text{C}$.

